

Evaluation of interfacial stress in fibre reinforced composites using the slice compression test.

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ABSTRACT

The slice compression test is a novel technique for measuring the interfacial shear stress in fibre reinforced composites. The composite slice is compressed between a ceramic anvil, where there is a constant strain condition, and a ductile metal replica, where there is a constant stress condition. The modulus mismatch between fibre and matrix results in debonding of the interface and then interfacial sliding. Measurement of fibre protrusion heights enables calculation of the interfacial shear stress. The technique has been investigated for a range of composite systems including SiC monofilament reinforced metal and ceramic matrices, carbon fibre reinforced ceramics and SiC reinforced glass-ceramics. Particular attention has been paid to testing conditions to avoid the onset of matrix cracking which results in erroneous measurements of fibre protrusion length. It was found that, with optimised loading conditions, the results for all composite systems compare well with those found using other techniques.

INTRODUCTION

Ceramic matrix composites (CMCs) have the potential for high temperature use by having an improved fracture toughness when compared with monolithic ceramics. In fibre-reinforced ceramics the principal mechanism which increases fracture toughness is energy absorption by fibre-matrix debonding followed by fibre pull-out [1]. Thus, the interfacial frictional shear strength (τ_f) of the fibre-matrix interface is one of the governing properties on which fracture toughness depends.

A number of techniques exist for evaluating interfacial properties in fibre reinforced composites, the majority being based on single fibre push in or pull out geometries. The slice compression test (SCT), developed by Shafry and Brandon, is a relatively new method for determining τ_f [2], involving the compression of a composite slice between a hard ceramic anvil and a ductile metal replica. The technique assumes a constant stress condition at the replica surface. Due to the fibre/matrix elastic modulus mismatch, debonding is initiated and the fibre is displaced relative

to the matrix, resulting in fibre protrusion in the case of higher fibre modulus. The metal replica is plastically deformed and retains an imprint of fibre protrusion at maximum applied stress. The fibre partially relaxes on removal of applied stress leaving a residual protrusion. Measurement of peak and residual protrusion heights enables the calculation of τ_f .

The SCT offers the possibility of multiple fibre testing and hence more representative results for a given composite system. It is also easier to adapt for high temperature use than single fibre methods. However, most work done using this technique has resulted in anomalously low τ_f values [2,3].

There are a number of possible reasons for the inconsistencies found using this testing method:

- i) assumptions used in the analysis
- ii) the testing configuration and
- iii) the fibre displacement measurements.

The analysis for the SCT is based on Marshall and Oliver's analysis for fibre microindentation [4]. In the slice compression test the Poisson's effect will induce a tensile stress across the fibre/matrix interface, for the particular composite systems studied. For the indenter based techniques the stress induced at the interface is compressive. Therefore, the compression slice test should give lower values for τ_f than the indenter based techniques. However, crack spacing measurement from tensile testing should have a Poisson ratio effect of the same sign as the SCT, but this technique does not produce results which are very different from indentation methods. More recently, Hsueh has developed a more rigorous approach which takes into account Poisson's ratio effects, residual stresses and differentiates between the interfacial debond stress and the interfacial frictional stress [5]. Other work has focused on accounting for the difference in fibre and matrix stress at the aluminium surface [3] and the effect of degree of fibre misalignment [6].

It is also possible that the testing conditions are at fault. A large compressive stress applied to a composite specimen can induce matrix microcracking. It is clear that cracking reduces the constraining influence of the matrix on the fibres, allowing fibres to protrude more and hence give lower τ_f values. Therefore, loading conditions should be such as to minimise matrix damage.

It is assumed in all analyses that the replica material behaves ideally, deforming plastically without significant shear at the edges. Therefore, the replica material must have a suitable working range of stresses for a given composite system. For glass-ceramic matrices this has been found to be annealed grade 1100 aluminium. It is also necessary for the plastic zone to be contained within the replica, defining the minimum size of the aluminium [6].

A source of error in this technique is inaccurate measurement of fibre protrusion. For low applied stress, the fibre displacements are low, $<0.1\mu\text{m}$. Thus, it is imperative to examine the composite specimen surface to evaluate the extent of fibre protrusion prior to testing to account for preferential polishing effects.

EXPERIMENT AND ANALYSES

The compression slice test, involves the compression of a CMC sample between silicon nitride and commercially pure aluminium (grade 1100). The composite material is cut and polished normal to the fibre axis on both faces. The silicon nitride and aluminium are also polished to 1/4 μ m finish.

During loading, the aluminium top plate imposes a condition of approximate uniform stress on the composite upper surface. The silicon nitride imposes a condition of approximate uniform strain on the bottom surface of the composite. The maximum elastic strain mismatch is thus at the upper surface of the composite slice. As the load is increased debonding of the fibre-matrix interface is initiated at the top surface and propagates downwards. If the fibre reinforcement in the composite has a higher Young's modulus than the matrix, there will be fibre protrusion from the top surface. The loading is taken to a peak stress (σ_a). Once unloaded the fibres partially relax back into the composite surface leaving a residual protrusion. The aluminium bears an imprint of the composite surface at peak stress and hence maximum fibre protrusion.

Measurement of maximum and residual protrusion heights is necessary to enable calculation of the interfacial shear stress (τ_f). It is assumed that at the top surface the axial stress in both fibre and matrix is the applied stress, σ_a . The axial strains are taken to be identical in the fibre and matrix at the bottom surface. It is assumed that the shear stress τ_f is constant and localised at the interface. Thus, τ_f is:

$$\tau_f = \frac{R(1 - V_f)\sigma_a^2(E_f - E_m)^2}{4\delta E_m E_f E_c} \quad (1)$$

where V_f is the local fibre volume fraction, σ_a the applied stress, R the radius of the fibre, δ is the fibre protrusion height and E_f , E_m and E_c are the elastic moduli for the fibre, matrix and composite respectively ($E_c = E_f V_f + E_m(1 - V_f)$ from the law of mixtures). However, in calculating τ_f , the bulk fibre volume fraction was used as this gave sufficient accuracy.

Hsueh has re-analysed the compression slice test to include the effect of interfacial bonding, Poisson's expansion and residual stresses. The aim of this analysis is to determine the residual clamping stress on the fibre (σ_c), the interfacial radial stress induced by Poisson's effect and the loading stress (σ_p), the axial stress in the fibre (σ_{fz}) and the coefficient of friction at the interface (μ). The interfacial shear stress is assumed to be constant along the interface and is defined as:

$$\tau_f = \pm\mu(\sigma_c + \bar{\sigma}_p) \quad (2)$$

For a fibre of radius a in a representative volume element of radius, b , where $b^2 = a^2/f$, f being the fibre volume fraction, Hsueh has established a relationship between σ_c and σ_{fz} based on thermomechanical mismatch between fibre and matrix, given in Eqn (3) for the case where the fibre thermal expansion coefficient is isotropic.

$$\frac{\sigma_{fz}}{\sigma_c} = \frac{(1 - f)(1 + \nu_f)E_m + (1 + f)(1 + \nu_m)E_f}{(1 - f)(1 + \nu_f)E_m + f(1 + \nu_m)E_f} \quad (3)$$

where ν_m and ν_f are the Poisson's expansion coefficients for the matrix and fibre respectively.

Fibre displacements are defined in Eqns (4) and (5).

$$\Delta u^* = \frac{b^2 h^* E_c}{2(b^2 - a^2) E_f E_m} \left[\left(1 - \frac{E_f}{E_c} \right) \sigma^* - \frac{(b^2 - a^2)}{b^2 E_c} (E_f - E_m) \sigma_d - 2\sigma_{fz} \right] \quad (4)$$

where Δu^* is the peak fibre displacement, h^* is the peak sliding zone length, σ^* is the peak applied stress and σ_d is the debond stress.

$$\Delta u_u = \frac{b^2 h^* E_c}{2(b^2 - a^2) E_f E_m} \left[\left(1 - \frac{2E_f}{E_c} \right) \sigma + \sigma_{fu} - \left(1 - \frac{E_f}{E_c} \right) \sigma^* + \frac{(b^2 - a^2)(E_f - E_m) \sigma_d}{b^2 E_c} \right] \quad (5)$$

where Δu_u is the change in protrusion height due to unloading, σ is the applied stress and σ_{fu} is the axial stress in the fibre on unloading. σ_{fu} defined as:

$$\sigma_{fu} = \sigma - \left[\left(1 - \frac{E_f}{E_c} \right) \sigma^* + \frac{(b^2 - a^2)(E_f - E_m) \sigma_d}{b^2 E_c} \right] \frac{\bar{\tau}_u}{\bar{\tau}^*} \quad (6)$$

where $\bar{\tau}_u$ and $\bar{\tau}^*$ are the average interfacial shear stresses for unloading and loading respectively. $\bar{\tau}_u$ and $\bar{\tau}^*$ are given by Eqns (7) and (8). Eqn (8) is for the unloading sliding zone length, $h_u = h^*$, the peak sliding zone length.

$$\bar{\tau}_u = \frac{-\mu \left[D\sigma_c + \left(\frac{\nu_f E_m}{E_f} - \nu_m \right) \sigma \right]}{D - \frac{\mu}{2\bar{\tau}^*} \left(\frac{\nu_f E_m}{E_f} + \frac{a^2 \nu_m}{b^2 - a^2} \right) \left[\left(1 - \frac{E_f}{E_c} \right) \sigma^* + \frac{(b^2 - a^2)(E_f - E_m) \sigma_d}{b^2 E_c} \right]} \quad (7)$$

$$\bar{\tau}^* = \frac{\mu}{2D} \left\{ 2D\sigma_c + \left[\left(\frac{\nu_f E_m}{E_f} + \frac{a^2 \nu_m}{b^2 - a^2} \right) \left(1 + \frac{E_f}{E_c} \right) - \frac{2b^2 \nu_m}{b^2 - a^2} \right] \sigma^* - \left(\frac{\nu_f E_m}{E_f} + \frac{a^2 \nu_m}{b^2 - a^2} \right) \frac{(b^2 - a^2)(E_f - E_m) \sigma_d}{b^2 E_c} \right\} \quad (8)$$

where D is a constant for the particular fibre being tested:

$$D = \frac{b^2 + a^2}{b^2 - a^2} + \nu_m + \frac{(1 - \nu_f) E_m}{E_f} \quad (9)$$

$\bar{\sigma}_p$ is the average radial stress and is defined as:

$$\bar{\sigma}_p = \frac{\left(\left(\frac{\nu_f E_m}{E_f} + \frac{a^2 \nu_m}{b^2 - a^2} \right) \left(1 + \frac{E_f}{E_c} \right) - \frac{2b^2 \nu_m}{b^2 - a^2} \right) \sigma^* - \left(\frac{\nu_f E_m}{E_f} + \frac{a^2 \nu_m}{b^2 - a^2} \right) \left(\frac{(b^2 - a^2)(E_f - E_m) \sigma_d}{b^2 E_c} \right)}{2D} \quad (10)$$

The stress-sliding zone relationship is given in Eqn (11).

$$\sigma^* = \frac{-\left[1 - \frac{h^* \mu}{aD} \left(\frac{v_f E_m}{E_f} + \frac{a^2 v_m}{b^2 - a^2} \right)\right] (b^2 - a^2) (E_f - E_m) \sigma_d - \frac{2h^* \mu \sigma_c}{a}}{1 - \frac{E_f}{E_c} + \frac{h^* \mu}{aD} \left[\left(\frac{v_f E_m}{E_f} + \frac{a^2 v_m}{b^2 - a^2} \right) \left(1 + \frac{E_f}{E_c} \right) - \frac{2b^2 v_m}{b^2 - a^2} \right]} \quad (11)$$

It is possible to obtain σ_c and hence σ_{fz} from the ratio of Δu_0 to Δu^* , the residual and peak protrusions respectively, where Δu_0 is the sum of Δu^* and Δu_1 .

In all the tests performed, fibres are displaced relative to the matrix surface. It is important to have an accurate measurement of this displacement and thus, it is important to have a flat, crack-free composite surface. It is essential to minimise preferential polishing as this will also lead to a misleading measurement of fibre displacement. Interferometry techniques and AFM have been used to measure $\leq 0.1 \mu\text{m}$ protrusions.

Initial testing was based on LAS-III/SiC, from United Technologies, and borosilicate 7740/SiC, from Harwell. Further work included: SiC monofilament reinforced Sialon, from DRA Farnborough, monofilament reinforced Ti-6Al-4V, from Textron Speciality Materials, and carbon fibre and Hi Nicalon reinforced Si_3N_4 , fabricated at IAM, JRC, Petten.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

INITIAL TESTING

The compression slice test results given in Table 1, though lower than values found using other techniques, are in agreement with the original work done by Shafry and Brandon [2]. τ_f values for LAS/SiC ranged between 0.06 and 0.28 MPa, and for 7740/SiC between 0.3 and 0.7 MPa. However, there is a large discrepancy between these τ_f values and those found using other techniques and clearly this cannot be attributed to experimental error alone.

Table 1. Initial slice compression test results using Brandon analysis.

Composite system	σ_a (MPa)	δ (μm)	τ_f (MPa)
7740/SiC	129	0.63-3.05	0.03-0.55
LAS-III/SiC	186	0.89-2.82	0.06-0.33

A closer look at SEM micrographs of composite or replica surfaces after testing show clearly the presence of matrix microcracking, see Fig. 1 where the aluminium has been pushed into matrix cracks - indicated by arrows. In some specimens fibre protrusions were only observed between laminates and on the edges of the specimen tested. This suggests that it is not possible to measure fibre protrusion in the rest of the sample because the protrusions are too small to resolve using the SEM. Thus, interferometry techniques were employed to measure these small protrusions. This resulted in revised δ measurements and hence an increase in the calculated τ_f , see Table 2.

Figure 1. SEM micrograph of fibre protrusion impression in aluminium from SCT testing of LAS-III/SiC.

Table 2. Revised slice compression test results using Brandon analysis.

Composite system	σ_a (MPa)	δ (μm)	τ_f (MPa)
7740/SiC	129	0.1 - 0.4	0.35 - 0.9
LAS-III/SiC	186	0.15 - 0.75	0.3 - 0.75

Protrusion height measurements were selected from regions of the specimen that appear to have undergone little matrix microcracking. However, the results are still low when compared with other interfacial testing methods [7]. This could be due to a number of reasons: the Poisson's effect is not accounted for, the interface is in tension rather than compression as in the case of fibre push in, and the presence of some microcracking.

NEW SYSTEMS

For the glass-ceramic matrix systems a reduction of the applied stress to minimise microcracking leads to fibre protrusion height measurements that are $<0.1\mu\text{m}$ and in some cases cannot be distinguished from fibre relief due to polishing. Therefore, the technique has been applied to systems less susceptible to matrix cracking: a metal matrix monofilament reinforced system (Ti-6Al-4V with Textron fibres), a Textron monofilament reinforced Sialon matrix, carbon fibre reinforced Si_3N_4 with a B_4C and SiC fibre coating and carbon coated Hi Nicalon reinforced Si_3N_4 .

Interferometry was used for preliminary examination of the composite surfaces. Fibre protrusion measurement after testing must, therefore, be the protrusion measured minus the original fibre relief before testing.

Table 3. Compression slice test results for new systems using Brandon analysis.

Composite system	σ_a (MPa)	δ (μm)	τ_f (MPa)
Ti-6Al-4V/SiC	362	0.04 - 0.06	223 - 357
Sialon/SiC	260	6.6	0.59
Si ₃ N ₄ /B ₄ C/C	565	0.2 - 0.6	0.4 - 4.3
Si ₃ N ₄ /SiC/C	450	0.1 - 0.7	3.3 - 11.3
Si ₃ N ₄ /C/Hi-SiC	560	0.34	95

The results quoted in each case are the result of a series of tests carried out to find the correct applied stress - this being sufficient load to cause fibre protrusions clearly greater than relief due to polishing effects, but low enough not to cause obvious matrix microcracking. Fig. 2 shows a micrograph of residual fibre protrusion on the composite surface for Si₃N₄/B₄C/C - there is no obvious microcracking.

Figure 2. SEM micrograph of Si₃N₄/B₄C/C composite surface after testing.

τ_f for Ti-6-4 has been found to range from 120 - 240 MPa using push out and fragmentation techniques [8]. This suggests the compression slice test gives slightly higher values for τ_f for Ti-6-4. This is also true for Si₃N₄/Hi-Nicalon, where the SCT gives realistic but higher values than indentation [9]. Si₃N₄/Carbon systems and Sialon/SiC are newly developed and are expected to possess a low τ_f . Thus, the use of optimised testing conditions with Brandon's analysis gives realistic values for τ_f for the systems investigated.

Hsueh's analysis has been applied to the Ti-6Al-4V and Sialon systems. It was not possible to obtain real solutions for the Ti-6Al-4V system. Sialon/SiC gave $\sigma_c = -16.4$ MPa, with $\mu = 0.002$ and an estimated $\tau_f = 0.061$. This is more of an underestimate than the Brandon analysis gives. Hsueh has used results from Brandon's original paper [2] for LAS-III/SiC and finds σ_c to be -11.3 MPa and μ to be 0.0985. Having used this analysis and data τ_f is still slightly lower than in indentation techniques [5].

Hsueh suggests that during unloading the condition of uniform stress is no longer valid and therefore the analyses for unloading are hypothetical [10]. However, these analyses are necessary in calculating a solution from residual and peak protrusion measurements. It is also noted that the $\sigma_c - \sigma_{fz}$ relationship will vary due to interfacial asperities. These are then possible sources of error.

CONCLUSIONS

It has been shown that, with optimised test conditions and careful measurement of fibre protrusion, the slice compression test using Brandon's analysis produces interfacial shear stress results in reasonable agreement with those found using other techniques. The use of Hsueh's analysis provides a more detailed stress analysis, which however may not be applicable in all cases.

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